

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation
framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's
type index of the Psalms.

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Abstract

The Psalms have been called the prayers and praise of the people. Through the centuries, the Psalms have given voice to the voiceless, prayers to the prayerless, and hope to the hopeless. Whereas the rest of the Bible is seen as the voice of God, the Psalms are the voices of the people with God. In his seminal work on the Psalms, Walter Brueggemann suggests three places or seasons found in the Psalms. According to Brueggemann, the Psalms can be roughly grouped around three themes: poems of orientation, disorientation, and new orientation. He identifies certain movements in the Psalms that correlate with the lives of the faithful: the movement from Orientation to Disorientation and the movement from Disorientation to a New Orientation. This framework fits the realities of people's lived stories and how life stories repeatedly fit into these three seasons. Human life consists of satisfied seasons of well-being, angry seasons of hurt and death, and seasons of breakthroughs and joy. In this paper, I draw from Brueggemann's pastoral reading of the Psalms to introduce a framework for pastoral care or, as I preferred, *seelsorge*, formulated as: "*Toward an orientation-disorientation-new orientation framework in the practice of pastoral care, based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms.*"

Key Words: Seelsorge; ODNO – orientation-disorientation-new orientation; seelsorger; saturated story².

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Introduction

All life is a journey, not a home; it is a road, not the country; and those transient enjoyments which you have in this life, lawful in their way—those incidental and evanescent pleasures which you may sip—are not home, they are little inns only upon the road-side of life, where you are refreshed for a moment, that you may take the pilgrim-staff and journey on again, seeking what is still before you—the rest that remains. (Anonymous)³

The Orientation-Disorientation-New Orientation framework for pastoral care is not merely a new method or tool for ministry but a way of thinking about the Psalms, the bible, and life itself. During my graduate studies in the Psalm in 2003, I was very fortunate to have as mentor and study leader a scholar of the Psalms who broadened my scope of studies beyond a mere clinical and exegetical study of the Psalms. I was introduced to the works of Walter Brueggemann on the Psalms. His pastoral readings of the Psalms intrigued me further to explore the world of pastoral care through the Psalms. It also resonated with my own life and journey and influenced my thinking. During the same time, I was introduced to the world of narrative psychology and therapy. Combined with the Psalms studies, the Narrative Therapy studies also opened up new possibilities

³ Life Is a Journey, Not a Destination – Quote Investigator®.
<https://quoteinvestigator.com/2012/08/31/life-journey/>

for my ministry and approach to pastoral care. It brought me to the development of the ODNO framework for the way I approached ministry and pastoral care. As the years went by, I sought to develop it as a significant conceptional theory and way of thinking in my therapeutic practice.

I have labeled the ODNO a *framework* for pastoral care/*seelsorge*² with particular reference to pastoral care and not counseling. I think of pastoral care in the historical sense of *seelsorge*. Modern pastoral counseling has been dramatically influenced by disciplines of humanity such as psychology which put it in specialized therapy. *Seelsorge*, or care for the soul, brings pastoral care back to the community of faith, which includes the role of the pastor but is not exclusively the pastor's work. Pastoral care, or *seelsorge*, is the work of wholeness, body, spirit, and soul. It includes the entire person in all its dimensions and aspects.

I have also employed some principles of the narrative approach to care. According to this approach, based on the works of David Epston, Michael White, Jill Freedman, Gene Combs, et al.,³ people construct their lives with stories. The

²Luther has seen *Seelsorge* as the mutual cure and care of the souls of Christians for one another. According to William A. Clebsch and Charles R. Jaekle, it consists of helping acts done by Christians and clergy directed toward the healing, guiding, sustaining, and reconciling of troubled persons whose troubles arise in the context of ultimate meanings and concerns. Pastoral Care | Laura Vivanco. <https://www.vivanco.me.uk/faith-love-hope-and-popular-romance-fiction/4-pastoral-care>

³Jill Freedman, Gene Combs, 1996, *Doing Narrative Therapy*, WW Norton.

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. stories stored in our memories create the framework of our attempts to discover meaning in life, and it also aids our approach to the future.

Stories are, therefore, not merely ways to describe our lives; they are much more than simple descriptions. Our stories give form to our lives. As such, we organize our lives and try to provide handholds, which will help us by step to cross the unstable rope bridge towards our future.

The point of departure and the basis of the narrative approach is that unity exists between the past, the present, and the future and simultaneously contains an inherent tension. Through telling our stories, we try to express and work with the unity and tension between the past, present, and future. A narrative approach to dialogue and therapy is about mining these stories, continuously being told by people, so they can eventually be reformulated into stories that would give new meaning and impetus to life. This unity of human existence, which includes the past, present, and future, has been neglected in the past by most behavioral and social sciences. The well-known psychoanalytical models⁴ are based on a personality theory, which seeks to explain human behavior due to suppressed sexual and aggressive

⁴ Paul V. Trad, 2007, *Psychoanalytic models. Paradigms and paradoxes*, Taylor and Francis Online, Pages 155-16, Published online: 24 Dec 2007

instincts rooted in the distant past. The point of departure is that things in the past need to be “treated,” and then the individual is supposed to function optimally. Other theories, including theories of family therapy, are more inclined to emphasize the immediate and functionality. The future and the unity between future, present, and past still do not receive adequate emphasis. The meaning of the future and the unity of the human story, which encompasses the whole “journey,” is a discovery that offers terrific possibilities for a better understanding of human living.

Walter Brueggemann described the Christian life as “telling a past and dreaming a future”⁵ This also describes our whole existence. Our stories contain elements of telling and dreaming. The more significant the gap between the “telling” and the “dreaming” becomes, the more the tension will increase and the more the likelihood of pathological behavior. On the other hand, where harmony exists between yesterday, today, and tomorrow, there will be integrity, wholeness, and maturity – the essential ingredients of spirituality.”

The central theme proposed in this work is transitioning

⁵ As retrieved from J. C. M, J. Laas, 2000, Telling a past, dreaming a future' (Walter Brueggemann) - Die essensie van die narratiewe pastoraat, *Verbum et Ecclesia* | *Skrif en Kerk*: Vol 21, No 2 | a1261 | DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4102/ve.v21i2.1261>.

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. from life (orientation) to LIFE (new orientation) through the trauma of disorientation. A new orientation also implies the process of dying to the old life (disorientation). Two movements carry this theme to its conclusion: from orientation to disorientation and then new orientation.

The sole purpose of this paper is to stimulate conversation about the ideas set forward. This is indeed not the end product but part of the ongoing search for better ways to pastorally aid people in their search for wholeness from a settled past through an unsettled season to a surprising future of wholeness and new horizons.

First Movement: Orientation: I Am.

Brueggemann suggests that human beings “regularly find themselves in one of three places: a place of orientation, in which everything makes sense in our lives; a place of disorientation, in which we feel we have sunk into the pit; and a place of new orientation, in which we realize that God has lifted us out of the pit and we are in a new place full of gratitude and awareness about our lives and our God. Using these three “places,” Brueggemann suggests that life has a rhythm as we move from one place to the next.”⁴ He believes that The Psalms

⁴ Blogging Towards Sunday, June 11, 2017 | CAPC Oakland.
<https://capcoakland.me/2017/06/07/blogging-towards-sunday-june-11-2017/>

match those places and the surprisingly painful and joyful moves we make. According to Brueggemann, the Psalms of Orientation express a confident, serene settlement of faith issues. God is known to be reliable and trustworthy. The particular faith community has decided to trust in this particular God. They describe a happy, blessed state and confidence in the abiding, reliable gifts of life from God. Life is not troubled or threatened but is seen as the well-ordered world intended by God. This is a “no surprise world” and, consequently, a world of “no fear.” The Psalms do not report on an event, a happening, or an intrusion. Instead, they describe how things are.

Psalms of orientation reflect the ordinariness of life. Most people spend a large part of their lives in this place. Things are settled, and life makes sense for the most part. They have a sense of confidence in the regularity of life and God’s creation. Several psalms express this outlook, articulating a confidence that the world is orderly due to God’s wisdom built into the world at the time of creation. We find in these psalms a sense that good people prosper and the wicked are punished. They express the conviction that God is the one who guarantees life and protects it. Psalm 1 is a typical example of the Psalms of orientation. According to Brueggemann, Psalm 1 affirms that the well-orientated life fixed on the Torah is one of happiness and well-being. There is no neutral ground – either be a happy

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. person who enjoys obedience to the Torah (v. 1-2) or be the wicked who refuse such a delight (v. 4). That is how life is and how the world works. There is no ambiguity or doubt. The place of orientation is a settled one, laying the foundations of life and settling the believer's identity. In the life of Christ, it is represented in His life and baptism. In the life of a Christian, the place of orientation represents the sureness of God's love, forgiveness, and acceptance. There are the sure foundations, the unchangeable truths, and the eternal fidelity of God.

The place of orientation also suggests a darker side. The dominant story of orientation influences the formation of an identity, beliefs, and life patterns. However, in forming identity, this place of orientation can form a true identity that is strong and sustainable.

Thus, in a manipulative social construct, this place of orientation can also create a false self, a false reality, and even an adopted identity. The identity is formed by an inner discourse of being, environmental circumstances, and external discourses. The person can become a product or even a victim of social constructs. Social discourses and constructs can include the voice and influence of religion, church, school, family, culture, etc.

Regarding identity, I would like to call this place the “**I am.**” “I am.” has a punctuation period indicating the supposed status quo or flowing within the stream of social

constructs. “I am.” is the sum total of the expectations of the micro and even macro society and the individual’s attempts to fit into that construct, be it social, cultural, religious, or familial. What at first seems to be a safe and well-ordered orientation might change into a new reality of disorientated, distorting the “**I am.**” A healthy “I am.” is only possible if the environment allows individuals to grow into their identity and find their voice and core self. It is, however, possible for the “**I am.**” to be squashed and reformed into the group’s image or expectations of the environment.

This is well illustrated by the movie *The Truman Show*.⁶ In this movie, Truman is a man whose life is fake. The place where he lives is a big studio with hidden cameras everywhere, and all his friends and people around him are actors who play their roles in the most popular TV series in the world: The Truman Show. Truman thinks he is an ordinary man with an ordinary life and has no idea how he is exploited. Until one day... he finds out everything. The same happens with a person growing up in a particular environment where the authentic self is suppressed and sometimes abused. This describes the place of orientation on

⁶ IMDB. 1998, <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0120382/>.

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a macro level. It could comprise a set of religious beliefs a person grew up with or a false view of them or others. Examples are people growing up during Apartheid in South Africa or under Communism in other areas. Another example is growing up in a religion, faith, or cult.

Further to identity-forming, the following: Identity formation is mainly seen as the development of the distinct personality of an individual regarded as a persisting entity in a particular stage of life in which individual characteristics are possessed and by which a person is recognized or known (such as the establishment of a reputation). This process defines individuals to others and themselves. Pieces of the entity's identity include a sense of continuity, a sense of uniqueness from others, and a sense of affiliation. Identity formation leads to several issues of personal identity and an identity where the individual has some comprehension of him or herself as a discrete and separate entity. This may be through individuation, whereby the undifferentiated individual tends to become unique or undergoes stages through which differentiated facets of a person's life tend toward becoming a more indivisible whole. Identity is a specific way of thinking about oneself that emerges during adolescence. It involves a sense of self-unity, accompanied by a feeling that the self has continuity over time. A firmly

established identity also provides a sense of uniqueness as a person.

Allow me to illustrate this in the story of Peter⁷. In Peter's life, this meant the 'safe' environment of his upbringing. The framing story of his life was one of orderliness, with very few gray areas. Protected and shaped by the church, his family values, and the construct of society, Peter's worldview was that God was reliable, the world safe, and the future bright. In his world, people marry, produce offspring, succeed in their vocation, and eventually die and go to heaven. Bad things happen, but faith in God will help him overcome the world and the temptations and tribulations thereof. His identity was firmly established in the *I-am.-* mode. From a narrative perspective, Peter's life was significantly authored by the constructs of his family, church, society, and culture. Alice Morgan (Morgan:2000) says: "Our lives are multistoried. Many stories coincide, and different stories can be told about the same events. No single story can be free of ambiguity or contradiction, and no single story can encapsulate or handle all the contingencies of life." Narrative therapy holds that our identities are shaped by the accounts of our lives found in our stories or narratives.

⁷ The name has been changed to protect the individual's identity.

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The dominant life story formed during his upbringing was conformation to society. Considering his strict religious convictions and the discourse of the church he belonged to, it is no wonder that he conformed to his environment. It has to be mentioned that Peter and his family belonged to an evangelical church whose doctrines are marked by a literal interpretation of the Bible. A clear distinction was made between born-again believers, believers, and non-believers. Peter's place of orientation was permeated by adapting and conforming to his church's doctrines and way of living. The place of orientation would soon be in turmoil. Orientation would soon turn into disorientation. It is essential to realize that disorientation can overlap and co-exist with orientation for a considerable period. For some people, the descent into disorientation could be gradual over time. For others, it is sudden during a crisis or trauma. The tipping point from orientation to disorientation was when a crisis forced him out of his orientated comfort zone into the un-comfortableness of disorientation. In Peter's life, his constructed reality came to a halting crisis when the COVID pandemic hit every foundation of his life. Peter lost his job and eventually had to face the reality that his entire identity settled in his career suddenly vanished. Moreover, his identity as husband also came under attack when his wife left him. Many other

changes occurred During this time, leaving him disillusioned and angry. His identity as a good father, husband, worker, and pastor within a well-ordered world came crashing down. I am. Became I am? Orientation moved into disorientation.

Second Movement: Disorientation – I Am?

The place or season of disorientation usually involves a crisis or life-changing events where the “I am.” or orientated persona conflicts with itself, resulting in an identity crisis. This is where learned values, realities, and much more are beginning to be questioned. As said, this might result from a crisis, trauma, or any life-challenging events. It is a place of instability and self-conflict. Brueggemann calls it “angry seasons of hurt, alienation, suffering, and death.” The duration of this phase or place in an individual’s life depends on various external and internal factors. During the phase, the “I am?” gets a question mark indicating the inner conflict, the attempts to find a new orientation, and even the desperate attempts for re-orientation. For any significant positive changes in a person’s life, the period or place of disorientation is paramount.

In the healing process, the experience of disorientation seems to align with that of Biblical figures in history. In the Psalms, Brueggemann identifies a significant number he

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labels "Psalms of Darkness."⁸ According to him, life in these

Psalms is a pilgrimage or process through the darkness that

belongs appropriately to humanness. "The presupposition and affirmation of these Psalms are that precisely in such

deathly places as presented in these Psalms; God gives new

life. The denial may be of a broken relationship, a lost career,

a medical diagnosis, or a major change in life. The harsh and

abrasive language of disorientation may penetrate the

deception and say, "No, this is how it is." Brueggemann

concedes that it is no wonder that the church has avoided

these Psalms. They lead us into a dangerous

acknowledgment of what hell life might be, where

everything is not polite and civil. They lead us away from

the comfortable religious claims of "modernity" in which

everything is money and control – very much a "religion of

orientation." The remarkable thing about Israel is that it did

not banish or deny the darkness from its religious enterprise.

It embraces the darkness as the very stuff of new life. Indeed,

Israel seems to know that new life comes from nowhere else.

The Psalms identify with the emotions and deep-seated disorientation experienced by any individual. The period of

⁸ Silvia Purdie, Conversations,

<https://www.conversations.net.nz/brueggeman-on-psalms.html>, retrieved

August 5, 2023.

disorientation is an integral part of any crisis, whether the crisis is a result of the loss of a job or loved one or a long-term crisis unfolding, such as an identity crisis, as described in the narratives of many people. The honesty of the Psalms envelopes the raw emotions experienced during a period of disorientation.

The period of disorientation can thus be defined as a period of trauma or crisis in the life of an individual or group. Webster's Dictionary (1990) defines the word crisis as "a decisive or crucial time, stage, or event" (p. 171). Roberts (2000) relates that a crisis includes an upset in the individual's steady state. Roberts and Corcoran (2000) further elaborate: "A person in a crisis state has experienced a ... threatening ... or traumatic event, is in a vulnerable state, has failed to cope and lessen the stress or trauma through customary coping strategies, and thus enters into a state of disequilibrium" (p. 327). With regards to trauma the following: Fundamental to a perceived trauma is a shattering of the worldview (Herman, 1992; Roberts, 2000). In this outcome of a new worldview, there is no meaning, control, connection, safe place, or dependable individual (Herman, 1992; Ochberg, 1993). This new belief or scheme violates basic safety needs and thwarts human growth and healthy functioning (Maslow, 1968). Other perceived trauma

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. outcomes include disruptions in the psychic equilibrium, which alters the optimal arousal levels (Knox & Roberts, 2001; Roberts & Corcoran, 2000; Wilson, 1995). The psychological experience includes helplessness and disconnection (Herman; Valentine et al., 1998), powerlessness and loss of control (McFarlane, 2000), difficulty in communicating (Wright et al., 1997), and chronic or disrupted feelings of fear and vulnerability (Wilson, 1995). Trauma, crisis, and life-changing events dominate the periods of disorientation. The Psalms of disorientation give voice and expression to the stories of disorientation that include this crisis and trauma.

In a pastoral and narrative context, it is a place or season of externalization of the internalized chaos. The individual who experiences the chaos and trauma of disorientation will also experience guilt in expressing negative feelings towards God. Whereas in the period or stage of orientation, the 'I am.' is settled and generally at peace, the period of disorientation introduces a question mark to the self where the 'I am.' becomes the 'I am?'. Indeed, a time and place where the depths of emotional disruption become a reality and death a companion. Thus, in this period, individuals might even become suicidal due to deep despair and desperation to escape from the hell of disorientation. This is where the

Psalms play a pivotal role in the counselee's verbalization and externalization of inner conflict.

During the time of disorientation, the individual often experiences an identity crisis. As mentioned, the 'I am.' becomes the 'I am?'. Who am I? Where do I fit in, and how does this crisis change the real I? According to Erikson, an identity crisis is a time of intensive analysis and exploration of different ways of looking at oneself.

This intense place of disorientation is well illustrated by the German theologian Dietrich Bonhoeffer in his poem *Who am I?*⁹

Who Am I? by Dietrich Bonhoeffer

Who am I? They often tell me
I stepped from my cell's confinement
Calmly, cheerfully, firmly,
Like a Squire from his country house.

Who am I? They often tell me
I used to speak to my warders
Freely and friendly and clearly,
As though it were mine to command.

Who am I? They also tell me
I bore the days of misfortune

⁹ Dietrich Bonhoeffer, 1997m *Letters and Papers from Prison* Paperback, Touchstone, Updated edition (July 1, 1997).

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms.

Equably, smilingly, proudly,
like one accustomed to win.

Am I then really that which other men tell of?
Or am I only what I myself know of myself?
Restless and longing and sick, like a bird in a cage,
Struggling for breath, as though hands were
compressing my throat,
Yearning for colors, for flowers, for the voices of birds,
Thirsting for words of kindness, for neighborliness,
Tossing in expectations of significant events,
Powerlessly trembling for friends at an infinite distance,
Weary and empty at praying, at thinking, at making,
Faint and ready to say farewell to it all.

Who am I? This or the Other?
Am I one person today and tomorrow another?
Am I both at once? A hypocrite before others,
And before myself a contemptible woebegone
weakling?
Or is something within me still like a beaten army
Fleeing in disorder from victory already achieved?

Who am I? They mock me, these lonely questions of
mine.
Whoever I am, Thou knowest, O God,
I am thine!

In this place of disorientation, the individual can experience a loss of meaning and purpose. The overall awareness of the loss of the meaning of life is nearly too much to bear. During the most profound moments of despair and self-destruction, two thoughts and absolutes conflict: the

crisis of the ‘lost-ness’ of it all where nothing makes sense anymore and, on the other hand, the reality of the things that indeed supersede the despair and give purpose and meaning to one’s existence.

In dealing with Peter, whose life came to a crashing halt when he had to deal with a trauma that left him with hurt, anger, and total alienation, the reality of the “I Am?” is well illustrated. He even came to the point of suicide because of his void of identity and subsequent dark season of “I am?” During this time, the works of Viktor Frankl¹⁰ made much sense to him. Frankl’s central message is that humans have an inherent will to find a purpose or meaning in their lives. The individual is accountable for finding their meaning, which may be external to themselves, religious, or focused on relationships with others. Meaning and purpose are conceived in the definition of future goals, and this conception helps contextualize and transform the present state of mind. The dialectical process of a future goal transforming the present moment unleashes the authentic power of an individual. Once authentic power has been unleashed, the individual’s past can be viewed as a tapestry

¹⁰ Viktor Frankl was an Austrian psychiatrist and Holocaust survivor and the founder of logotherapy, a school of psychotherapy that describes a search for a life’s meaning as the central human motivational force.
<https://www.viktorfrankl.org/biography.html>.

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. where all experiences and events have converged to shape the present moment, and the present moment has meaning in the context of a future goal. Life, for Frankl, ultimately meant taking responsibility to find the correct answer to its problems and fulfilling the tasks that are continually set for each individual. Frankl applies this learning from his experiences in Nazi concentration camps to the development of Logotherapy, his theory of psychoanalysis. The ontological premise of Logotherapy ¹¹ is that all have an inherent will to find a purpose or meaning in life. Frustration with the will to find meaning can lead to neuroses, and the task of psychoanalysis is to assist the patient in finding meaning in their life. Therefore, the meaning of life is for the individual to live with meaning and purpose, howsoever defined by the individual. As Nietzsche said: "He who has a *why* to live for can bear with almost any *how*." ¹²

Regarding the narrative approach to the place of

¹¹ Melissa Madeson, 2020, Positive Psychology.com., Logotherapy: Viktor Frankl's Theory of Meaning. <https://positivepsychology.com/viktor-frankl-logotherapy/>

¹² Frankl's quote of the philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche.

The quote appears In his epic work *Man's Search for Meaning*, 2006, Beacon Press; 1st edition (June 1, 2006)

disorientation, the pastoral *seelsorger*/caregiver will deal with externalization and deconstruction. The narrative approach to pastoral care views problems as separate from the individual. Through externalizing conversations, the problem is set free to stand independently. To realize that ‘I am’ is not the problem but that the false self, as created by orientation, can be separated from the individual could be a breakthrough in the therapeutic process.

For Peter to learn that his core identity was not the settled orientation of his career, a position as husband and father. He was more than that. The roles of pastor, husband, and good father were settled and well-constructed. However, he was more than that. Even his subsequent depression was but one part of his identity. To arrive at this point and to see himself as multidimensional freed him from the burden of a stigmatized ‘I am.’ To get there, the disorientation of ‘I am?’ was the key to the door of new orientation. He had to face up to himself and his brokenness and reach for the new self in Christ. Without the breakdown and separation of the constructed orientated self, the new self would not have been able to emerge. His saturated story, which was his dominating narrative, was that of the conflicting “I am.” which turned into the chaotic “I am?” The effects of the saturated narrative reinforced this story. The saturated

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. narrative had to be deconstructed and externalized to find the alternative story and for Peter to begin re-authoring his new story or the new orientation.

Externalizing questions subvert the problem's power by undermining conclusions that have gone unquestioned and by creating space that allows for the collaborative investigation of the problem and its effects. The individual can experience the relationship without the problem's complete dominance. Externalization, an integral part of narrative therapy, is achieved by a discursive shift where problems become referred to as nouns and thus as separate objectified entities. Through collaborative conversations with the therapist, the individual is encouraged to choose a name for the problem or saturated (vasgeloopte)¹³ story. Externalization generates new territory that provides room for alternatives to be explored. An additional use of externalizing language is with solutions and resources. Externalization can invite an individual's sense of agency and reinvigorate engagement with the individual's skills, abilities, and knowledge.

Johnella Bird (2004), whose work is strongly identified

¹³ An Afrikaans expression for saturation or someone who has reached the dead-end of a journey.

with narrative therapy, describes the importance of what she terms “relational language.” Bird puts forth the use of language that resists creating a binary structure. Externalizing can produce a binary between the client and the externalized problem.

When using relational language, meanings are constantly renegotiated. The therapist and client are in ongoing conversations that grapple with meaning, frames of reference, and the clients’ lived experiences. Relational language invites active participation and presence.

Externalization with counselees often frees ‘imagination’ and ‘hope’ from the confinement and weight of relational problems. Externalization assists in generating opportunities for the collaborative construction of a person’s preferred relationship stories. Externalization provides a powerful means for inviting new possibilities.

In Peter’s case, externalizing his internalized trauma and fears opened up new horizons and hope. His tipping point was a suicide attempt and subsequent dealing with long-buried trauma that forced him to re-evaluate his life and options. The period of disorientation serves as the entrance to a place of new orientation. Before reaching that, he had to successfully deconstruct his orientation narrative and externalize deep-seated internalized problems and

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. discourses. Through externalizing and deconstruction, new possibilities were being freed up and explored. The saturated story became a story of hope, and a new future arose gradually.

The Third Movement: A New Orientation – I Am!

Following Brueggemann's route, the place of disorientation is usually followed by a new orientation. It is deliberately not called re-orientation. Re-orientation has the ring of returning to a basic orientation. A. new orientation captures the surprising freshness of transcendence.

This period of new orientation is not simply a return to 'normality' where everything is coherent again. The rhythm of life expressed in the Psalms is not circular. The new orientation is another stage in our journey. The experience of the pit has changed us, and the experience of God's grace has transformed our life. We cannot go back again. We now know something about life and God's way of fidelity that cannot permit a return to an earlier faith. The Psalms are not only personal prayers; they are, above all, "pilgrimage" prayers. Life becomes coherent once again, and the pilgrimage goes on. However, we must learn not to forget and pray the Psalms daily.

In his *Praying the Psalms*,¹⁴ Brueggemann has shown that

a significant move of the Psalms is from an ordered, reliable life to an existence that somehow has run amok. The

Psalms express that new reality of disorientation when everything in heaven and on earth seems skewed and in chaos when the ‘I am’ becomes the ‘I am?’ and identity finds

itself in a position of not-knowing. The experience of disorientation is expressed in many different ways. In the journey of any person, it may be the heart of the Psalter that is most helpful because we live in a society of denial and cover-up, and these Psalms provide a way for healing candor.

The Psalms regularly bear witness to the surprising gift of new life just when none had been expected. It suggests the surprising outcome, the unlocked future, and the twist in the

story that changes life from disorientation to a new orientation. The new orientation is not to return to the old stable orientation, although there is a temptation to return.

The Psalmist knows that we can never go home again.

Brueggemann concedes that the speaker and the community of faith are often “surprised by grace” when it merges in the present life a new possibility that is inexplicable, wrought by God’s mysterious power and

ed. Edition.

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. goodness. The newness cannot be explained, predicted, or programmed, and it can “tell, narrate, recite, testify, in amazement and gratitude, “lost in wonder, love, and praise.” He further states, “It is important that the form includes not only a statement of the problem. It also includes a statement of the resolution, culminating in praise and thanksgiving. Israel’s praise characteristically comes out of the depths, out of the pit from which we were surprised to come because the situation seemed irresolvable.”

The songs in the Psalms are not about the “natural” outcome of trouble but about the decisive transformation made possible by God, who causes new life when none seems possible. The lives of people and communities are never static, and they are always on the move.

When following the narrative approach to counseling, the therapist or pastoral counselor has to remember that often, by the time a person has come to therapy, the stories they have for themselves and their lives become entirely dominated by problems (disorientation) that work to oppress them. These are sometimes called ‘problem-saturated’ stories as seen within the period or phase of disorientation. These problem-saturated stories can also become identities (e.g., “I have always been a depressed person.”). These kinds of stories can also invite a powerful negative influence on

how people see their lives and capabilities (e.g., “I am hopeless”). Pastoral caregivers or *seelsorgers* collaborate with people in stepping away from problem-saturated and oppressive stories to discovering the ‘untold’ or new orientation stories, including the preferred accounts of people’s lives (their intentions, hopes, commitments, values, desires, and dreams). Counselors are constantly listening to the stories of people’s lives, cultures, and religions and looking for clues of knowledge and skills which might assist people to live by their preferred way of being. In narrative work, people are invited to make meaning of their stories. It is believed that people are skilled at describing their own stories and are allowed to describe their stories more richly and to make sense of their lives. It is the job of the *seelsorger* to help people improve that skill. Again, it is also their challenge to provide an opportunity to bring in other experiences that have been neglected. In narrative practice, these experiences are called “unique outcomes” or exceptions to the dominant story. Narrative therapy innovator Michael White reminds us that life is multi-storied, not a single story, so we seek to discover and enrich one’s subordinate storylines.

Pastoral counselors and caregivers often make the mistake of believing they have a better way for people to

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function and then become the author of people's stories. This is couched in techniques commonly called 're-framing,' or outlining strengths, reaffirming or congratulating people. While certainly quite popular in our culture, these techniques do not necessarily lead to long-term change for the better. They tend to center the counselor as the expert or authority, which some counselors graciously accept.

Unique outcomes within the framework of ODNO provide a starting point for rich story development and re-authoring conversations. The *seelsorger* seeks to understand the unique outcome, i.e., when the person's 'personal failure' did not apply. As the therapeutic conversation continues, the *seelsorger* builds a scaffold of questions encouraging people to enrich their stories and fill the gaps. This generally assists people to draw on their lived experience and tell their story in a whole new way or to re-author their own stories. The *seelsorger* encourages the individual to become curious and fascinated by their stories. These new storylines become more prosperous and deeply rooted in history and are named.

The story might now be called My new beginning or Live a new life in Peter's case. It is the *seelsorgers'* job not to praise or judge but to assist an individual in moving from what is known and familiar to them (Orientation) to what is possible to know and thus achieve (New Orientation). Re-

authoring conversations allow people to understand better what is happening in their lives (Disorientation) and to inhabit their own lives and relationships more fully. Thus, people become more acquainted with the knowledge and skills of their lives that will ultimately help address the current problems brought to counseling. It de-centers the counselor, allowing the individual to take front and center as the new author of their life story.

In essence, within a narrative approach, the focus is not on ‘experts’ solving problems but on people discovering through conversations the hopeful, preferred, and previously unrecognized and hidden possibilities within themselves and unseen storylines.

By re-authoring their lives, the place of new orientation requires the intention to assist persons in resolving their problems by (1) enabling them to separate their lives and relationships from knowledge/stories that are impoverishing – thin described and mostly molded by the discourses of the place of orientation; (2) assisting them in challenging practices of self and relationship that are subjugating as experienced in the place and journey of disorientation and (3) encouraging people to re-author their lives according to alternative knowledge/stories and practices of self and relationship that have preferred

Toward an Orientation-Disorientation-New orientation framework for pastoral care based on Walter Brueggemann's type index of the Psalms. outcomes as part of their journey of new orientation. It is essential to impose the hope of a new orientation/story throughout therapy.

In Peter's case, his new orientation requires remembering¹⁵ his life's sojourners, re-authoring his values, purpose, and goals, and re-evaluating his identity in Christ. His past and failures became one part of his identity, allowing him to explore new horizons and live a whole and purposeful life. Freed from the effects of self-hate and more, he could explore other aspects of his identity. The "I am." constructed and defined by external factors such as the church, family, and society gave way to a place of "I am?" where he had to break down the preferred stories about his past, identity, and values. This led to the new "I am!" where Peter could start living a new life in a re-evaluated story of hope. The 'I am.' that becomes the 'I am?' is eventually guided and journeyed to the 'I am!', a place of new orientation.

¹⁵ Re-membering conversations in therapy provide an opportunity for people to revise the memberships of their association of life: to upgrade some memberships and to downgrade others; to honour some memberships and to revoke others; to grant authority to some voices in regard to matters of one's personal identity, and to disqualify other voices with regard to this. It subscribes to the notion that some people are in our lives for a season, others for a reason and some for ever.

Conclusion

Life is like playing a violin solo in public and learning the instrument as one goes on. – Samuel Butler

In his book, *The Secret of Letting Go*, Guy Finley¹⁶ speaks about a cuckoo bird's habit of laying its eggs in the nest of other birds and leaving them to hatch. She hides and waits until the nesting bird flies away, leaving its eggs unguarded. The cuckoo then quickly lays one of her own in the nest. The unsuspecting other bird returns and dutifully nestles down on what it believes to be its clutch of eggs. The cuckoo chick hatches first and pushes the later weaker hatchlings out of the nest. In this way, the parent birds, not realizing the switch has occurred, spend all their energies nurturing something that does not belong to them. Finley concludes, "We too have been tricked into caring for a life that is not ours by unconsciously adopting a kind of substitute self." This "substitute self," or as Carl Jung calls it, the "persona," and Freud calls the "ego," is the orientated self. It is a social mask that thrives upon approval; it wants

¹⁶ Guy Finley, 2007, *The Secret of Letting Go* Paperback, Llewellyn Publications; Revised ed. edition (October 8, 2007).

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to control people and situations. The new 'I am!' is free of the old, does not feel superior to anyone, and is not fear-based. There is no compulsion to control and no inner struggle for approval of dominance over external events.

The new 'I am!' is a life re-authored. Within the ODNO framework and in the narrative approach, the re-authoring of stories is part of the outcome of therapy. This re-authoring is premised on the idea that people's lives and relationships are shaped by the very knowledge and stories that persons use to give meaning to their experiences and specific practices of self or relationships associated with this knowledge and stories. A re-authoring intends to assist persons in resolving problems by (1) enabling them to separate their lives and relationships from knowledge/stories that are impoverishing as in the orientation phase; (2) assisting them in challenging practices of self and relationship that are subjugating; and (3) encouraging persons to re-author their lives according to alternative knowledge/stories and practices of self and relationship that have preferred outcomes. It also implies a new search for meaning and a new journey for purposeful living.

The pastoral application here is that a new orientation is always possible and should be the final purpose of *seelsorge*. This new orientation suggests a new 'I am' in which the

the individual will find a new identity and live within that new “I am!” Indeed, a dance and a celebration. The Psalms serve as a guide and pastoral panacea to suggest and lead one into hope. The Psalms shouted out that there was hope, a new orientation, and a new beginning. With a new grip on hope and God, the journey in healing is progressing, and a new self-actualization is possible.

In the story of my client Peter, this new orientation and unique outcomes resulted in freedom from the effects of his saturated story. He re-member his life and found a new direction and goal in his life’s journey. The re-membering of his life took a lot of courage and strength. The new ‘members’ of his life are celebrating his journey and future. He no longer defines himself only in one aspect of his identity but has excelled above it and lived a meaningful life.

The Orientation-disorientation-new orientation dimension in *seelsorge* and within the scope of narrative therapy is something to explore further and develop. The last word about this has not been spoken, and my wish is that this paper will serve as the beginning of a further exploration into it.

¹⁴ Walter Brueggemann, 2007, *Praying the Psalms*, Second Edition: Engaging Scripture and the Life of the Spirit Paperback – Illustrated, Cascade Books; 2nd

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